

Fisher Constrained Extremization in Quantum Mechanics and Directional Motion

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 23, 2023

In classical mechanics, a free particle moves through x and t with $dx/dt=v=\text{constant}$. Given that x and t may be shifted, it is dx and dt which are important. For fixed dx , $dt(x)$ yields information about the “probability” for the particle to be in dx so to speak. Thus one does not really distinguish between deterministic and probabilistic descriptions in this scenario. A problem with the probabilistic picture, however, is that different v (or p values) have the same constant probability $P(x)=\text{constant}$ for free motion. In other words, $P(x)=\text{constant}$ does not distinguish either the magnitude or direction of v . Thus, information is lost.

Is it possible to restore this information and still maintain a probabilistic picture? The answer, given by free particle quantum mechanics, seems to be yes. The probabilistic approach is to assign a probability $P(x)$ to each x point. This probability must treat each x point as the same and yet give information about v or p . (We use p because it represents impulse and is linked to special relativity i.e. a 4-vector.) The key idea we argue is to consider the first order change in x space because one assigns a $P(x)$ to each x and different p values are linked with different motion from one x to another.. This is the way to distinguish the direction and magnitude of p , but nothing else we argue.

In such a case: $d/dx f(px) = \text{Constant } p f(px)$ ((1)), we argue, where f is an unknown function. We show that this function, which is odd in x , cannot be real i.e. one needs at least a pair of real functions comprising f . We note that the derivative only gives information about p , thus $df/dx /f = p$. We argue this implicitly means each x point has the “same weight” even though the pair of functions f are not constants. We next analyze the behaviour of the two pairs of functions comprising f and conclude that in order for $d/dx d/dx f = pp f$, each function of the pair must be converted into itself. Thus: $d/dx d/dx f_1 = -pp \text{Constant } f_1$ and a similar equation for f_2 where f_1, f_2 are the pair. These, however, are periodic equations. Thus the implicit idea of each x point carrying the same weight is equivalent to $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ being separately periodic. This is equivalent to constant modulus problem.

How is this linked to Shannon’s entropy or Fisher information extremization? We argue that ((1)) means that $\ln(P)$ does not carry enough information in this situation, while for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas it does. It is $d/dx \ln(P)$ which carries information about p and its direction. If one wishes to create a function which does not distinguish the sign of momentum, it still has to incorporate the information of motion in one direction i.e. $d/dx \ln(P) d/dx \ln(P)$. One may take the average of this (called Fisher’s information) instead of the average of $\ln(P)$ in Shannon’s entropy. To link with the above ideas, $P(x)=f_1(x)f_2(x)$ if one considers a bound problem with infinite potential walls. Then Fisher’s information becomes $df_1/dx df_2/dx$. The extremization of Fisher’s information subject to $\text{Integral } f_1(x)f_2(x)= 1$ leads to the periodic condition described above. This means, we argue, that for the case of pp , one cannot sense any change in either $f_1(x)$ or $f_2(x)$. $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ are used to indicate differences to an odd power of d/dx and so for an even, there is no informational change at the $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ level. This we argue is what Fisher’s information extremization with $\text{Integral } f_1 f_2 =1$ gives i.e. periodicity.

Determinism or Probability for a Free Particle?

A free particle moves in one dimension such that $dx/dt = v = \text{constant}$. If dx is a constant, $dt(x)$ determines the time spent in each dx . One might call this an unnormalized probability appearing in a so-called deterministic problem. In fact, this notion may be extended to a bound classical particle with $dt = \text{Constant}/v(x)$, where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$, is a probability.

An issue which exists with the above probabilistic scenario is that information is lost, in particular the direction and magnitude of v . At this point, we switch to p (momentum) as the variable of interest because it describes physical impulses and appears in a special relativistic 4-vector. If m_0 (rest mass is known), p gives v and vice versa. This begs the question: Can one retain a probabilistic scenario, i.e. map each x with a $P(x)$, ignore time as a variable, and still know p (magnitude and direction)? We argue that the answer is yes.

The problem is thus to retain a $P(x)$ for each x , yet also know p associated with $P(x)$. This p is constant and applies to each x point. It is linked with motion from one x point to another. We argue that in such a problem $P(x)$ is no longer sufficient to supply all information needed. One must utilize its first derivative d/dx . One has two pieces of information: $P(x)$ and:

$$d/dx P(x) = \text{constant } p P(x) \quad ((2))$$

We argue that ((2)) is a key idea and is based strictly on information. ((2)) allows one to distinguish between different p values, but still is associated somehow with each x point having the same weight. It may be further noticed that $d/dx P(x)$ only yields the new information p . $P(x)$ is unchanged by the derivative. This we argue implicitly means that each x point carries the same weight even though $P(x)$ is not a constant. ((2)) supplies two pieces of information: p and equal weight at each x (although this is implicit).

Thus $P(x) = P(px)$ and $P(px)$ must be odd in x . This immediately leads to a problem because setting $P(x) = 0$ at a chosen $x=0$ means $P(x+)$ is positive and $P(x-)$ negative. This breaks with classical probability. Furthermore such a function does not seem to represent equal weight at each x in any fashion. We propose that one requires a pair of functions:

$$f = (f_1(px), f_2(px)) \text{ or } f = f_1(px) + i f_2(px) \quad ((3)) \text{ where } f_1, f_2 \text{ are real.}$$

$f(px)$, however, must still be an odd function in x . In fact:

$$df/dx = (df_1/dx + i df_2/dx) = p \text{ constant } (f_1 + if_2) \quad ((4))$$

If $\text{constant} = a$ a real number, $f_2 = df_2/dx = p \text{ constant}$, but this means f_1 and f_2 are proportional to x which does not treat each x point with the same weight in any fashion. We consider the constant

to be purely imaginary. A complex constant $a+ib$ would add an x to $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ which is unwanted.

$$\text{If constant} = ib, \quad df_2/dx = p b f_1 \quad \text{and} \quad df_1/dx = -p f_2 b \quad ((5))$$

Taking the second derivative yields: $d^2/dx^2 f_2 = -p^2 b^2 f_2$ ((6))

((6)), however, is a periodic equation and a similar relation holds for f_1 so it is also periodic. Thus for the case of $d/dx d/dx$ which yields pp (for a free particle), eigenvalue equations hold for $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ separately. One does not need a mix of f_1 and f_2 required for $df/dx = p$ constant f because one does not deal with the two dimensions needed to show the direction of motion. Thus when considering $d/dx d/dx$ one loses information about direction and a simpler situation arises i.e. one with less information. This, we argue, allows one to analyse f_1 and f_2 separately without having them mix. The mix is only to show directional motion. Thus we argue that this problem is driven largely by information.

Equal Weight at Each X Point

We argued above that $df/dx = p$ constant f implicitly contains the notion of each x point carrying the same weight. It also gives rise to $d/dx d/dx f_1 = pp b f_1$ and $d/dx d/dx f_2 = -b pp f_2$. This periodicity allows one to consider f_1 and f_2 as components associated with a fixed modulus representing equal weight at each x . For example, $f_1(x) = \cos(px)$ and $f_2(x) = \sin(px)$ is a solution.

Fisher's Information

In the literature (1), it has been pointed out that one may extremize Fisher's information subject to a constraint $\int P(x)dx=1$ to obtain the Schrodinger equation. $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ are solutions of this equation for $V(x)=0$. We ask: Why should this be the case?

Fisher's information is a quantity from statistics given by:

$$I = \text{constant} \int dx \quad P(x) \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\} \quad ((7))$$

$P(x)$, however, is a classical probability i.e. real and between 0 and 1 and not a pair of functions f_1 and f_2 . Furthermore $f_1^2 + f_2^2 = 1$, but $1 = P(x)$ leads to a zero Fisher's information. If one, however, considers $+p, -p$ probability in an OR situation with $f_1 = \cos(px)$ and $f_2 = \sin(px)$, then: $P(x) = C \cos(px)\cos(px)$ could be used instead of the modulus 1 in ((7)). Fisher's information is then linked to $d/dx \cos(px) d/dx \cos(px)$. This ensures a positive value (like Expectation(xx) in the usual variance expression). Why does extremization of ((7)) subject to $\int C \cos(px)\cos(px) = 1$ work? $d/dx \ln(P)$ represents a spatial function which differs from $P(x)$. This is fine in the case of the first derivative which is associated with motion in one direction (actually a pair of functions is needed to fully describe one dimensional motion). For $d/dx d/dx$ one no longer distinguishes between forward and backwards motion i.e. information is lost. One does not need to demonstrate the same information as in the d/dx case which must show one function f_1 moving into the other i.e. $df_1/dx = p$ constant f_2 . In other words, $d/dx d/dx$ on $P(x)$ can only bring back pp and $P(x)$ which is already known. Extremization of Fisher's information

subject to integral $P(x) dx=1$ ensure this informational condition and leads to a periodic equation for $\cos(px)$ i.e.

$$d/dx d/dx \cos(px) = -p^2 \cos(px) \quad ((8))$$

Note: This may be used in both nonrelativistic and relativistic analysis.

((8)) basically states that extremization of Fisher's information subject to $\cos(px)$ does not yield any new information except p . $P(x)$ is already known in the constraint and its form is unchanged by $d/dx d/dx$.

Difference Between Extremizing Shannon's Information and Fisher's Information

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for a classical gas may be obtained by extremizing entropy $S = -k \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$, where e_i is the energy of a single particle in the gas, subject to the constraint $\sum_i P(e_i) = 1$. On the other hand, (1) suggests extremizing Fisher's information: $I = \text{constant} \int dx P(x) \{ d/dx \ln(P(x)) \}^2$ subject to the constraint $\int dx P(x) = 1$. One may ask why there should exist two different extremization procedures. We argue the reason is associated with the different kind of information involved.

Extremization of Shannon's entropy is associated with $P(e_i)$ which does not involve direction in space. There are a possible set of e_i choices and one is interested in $P(e_i)$ such that $\sum_i P(e_i) = 1$. In the case of a free particle, the variable is x not e_i , because one wishes to know the probability associated with a point x in space. This probability is clearly a constant for a free particle, but this loses all information about direction and magnitude v or (momentum p). This is vital information which needs to be incorporated in a probabilistic description of the problem. Thus $P(x)=\text{constant}$ does not suffice and so neither does Shannon's entropy which is only based on probability.

Different p values means a particle travels with different speeds and impulses along x . It seems $dP(x)/dx$ should yield information about p , i.e. $dP(px)/dx = \text{constant } p P(px)$. In other words, d/dx only retrieves information about p . This seems to imply each x point carries the same weight in a sense because $dP/dx / P = \text{constant } p$ which is the same at each x point. $dP/dx / P$ is a form which ultimately appears in a different "statistical" quantity, namely Fisher's information, although matters are still complicated.

$dP/x = \text{constant } p P$ implies a pair of functions $(f_1(x), f_2(x)) = f(px)$ such that $f(px)$ is odd in x . Analysis shows that for $d/dx d/dx$, which loses all information about direction of motion (while f_1 and f_2 together carry this information), f_1 and f_2 become decoupled and: $d/dx d/dx f_1 = -p^2 f_1$ and $d/dx d/dx f_2 = p^2 f_2$. Thus one has periodic functions such that their modulus is a constant i.e. each x point carries the same weight. If one considers $f(px) + f(-px) = 2f_1(px)$ if $f_1(px)$ is even and $f_2(px)$ odd, one may set $P(x) = f_1(px)f_1(px)$ in Fisher's information expression and extremize it to obtain a periodic differential equation if one uses the constraint $\int P(x)dx$. We argue this simply means that although $f_1(x)$ and df_1/dx are different functions (because of motion in space), losing information about this motion i.e. $d/dx d/dx$ means only obtains information p^2 with $f_1(px)$ remaining unchanged. We argue that information is the underlying

idea behind the various extremization procedures and even procedures not involving extremization i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ as an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$.

References

1. Plastino, A. and Plastino, A.R. Fisher's Information, thermodynamics and the Schrodinger equation (2011)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286024896_Fisher_information_thermodynamics_and_schrodinger_equation